

Chemical Correlation Database (CCDB)

Exposome Correlation and Interpretation Database (ECIDbase.org)

Version : April 2024

Introduction:

CCDB contains the curated and raw correlations among chemicals measured in human biospecimens, primarily blood and urine samples. Biomonitoring and metabolomics datasets (both targeted and untargeted) enable investigations on the blood exposome that includes both naturally occurring and synthetic or mass-produced chemicals. Reported chemicals can be correlated with each other for several reasons, including biochemical reactions, source and toxic effects. To deduce these interpretations, pairs of correlating chemicals can be mapped by biochemical and chemical relationships, including – a known reaction, predicted reaction, gene ontology, MeSH term, metabolic pathway, structural similarity, maximum common substructure and exposures. These correlations can be useful for discovering new mechanisms, assessing the toxic effects of chemical exposures, identifying new exposures, finding new metabolic products and prioritizing new therapeutic targets in the human metabolic pathways.

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How the CCDB database is being computed and curated ?

Biomonitoring and metabolomics datasets were obtained from CDC NHANES, NIEHS HHEAR, Metabolomics WorkBench, EBI MetaboLights, GNPS UCSD, ECHO DASH, and primary literature (SI datasets). Datasets from these sources are curated and re-formatted to a standardized format that can accommodate both targeted and untargeted chemical analysis assays. Inter-chemical correlations are computed using a spearman-coefficient test. To interpret the correlations, information available in the NCBI PubChem database is obtained for each chemical that has been linked with a PubChem Compound identifier. Data dictionaries and re-formatted datasets are periodically made available in the Zenodo repository, whenever allowed by the source agreements. We utilized the reactions, pathways, MeSH, Gene Ontology, metabolic pathways, patents, PubChem Fingerprints and SMILES code from the PubChem database to explain the observed correlations. A semi-automated approach is utilized for linking the pairs of chemicals with the information from PubChem. Correlations that have been interpreted are added to the curated set after expert's check.

How to query the database ?

Website <https://ccdb.ecidbase.org/> will load the CCDB online interface application (ReactJS) that is adopted from the OpenSearch Dashboard.

Step 1: Click on the triple bar symbol and then click on “Discover”. It will load the database search application.

The discover application view :

Search box allows a free full text query. Try searching “PFOS”

There are 29 hits in which PFOS has a correlation with another analyte in the NHANES database.

The screenshot shows the CCDB interface with a table of data. The table has three columns: **pvalueCorTest**, **pvalueGLM**, and **pairedCompleteCaseCount**. The data rows show values for these columns. On the left sidebar, under 'Search field names', the field **ecidid** is highlighted with a yellow callout containing a plus sign (+).

pvalueCorTest	pvalueGLM	pairedCompleteCaseCount
0.0e+00	1.5e-45	494
0.0e+00	1.5e-45	494
1.3e-15	5.2e-58	494
0.0e+00	2.3e-84	1,927
0.0e+00	1.8e-84	1,927
0.0e+00	1.5e-136	1,927
0.0e+00	1.3e-134	1,928

Clicking on the + sign on a field name, will show only the selected columns in the table.

The screenshot shows the CCDB interface with the 'Selected fields' and 'Available fields' sections on the left. The 'Selected fields' section contains **pvalueCorTest**, **pvalueGLM**, and **pairedCompleteCaseCount**. The 'Available fields' section contains **_id** and **_index**. A yellow callout points to an X sign on the **pvalueGLM** field in the 'Selected fields' section.

pvalueCorTest	pvalueGLM	pairedCompleteCaseCount
0.0e+00	1.5e-45	494
0.0e+00	1.5e-45	494
1.3e-15	5.2e-58	494
0.0e+00	2.3e-84	1,927
0.0e+00	1.8e-84	1,927

Selected fields are shown on the left. All the available fields are shown below it. Clicking on the X sign will remove the column from the table.

The screenshot shows the 'EDIT FILTER' dialog box. The field **coeffCorTest** is selected with the operator **is between** and the value **0.80**. The dialog also includes a 'Create custom label?' checkbox, 'Cancel', and 'Save' buttons.

Add filter button will load the component to create a filter, for example find all the correlations that are 0.80 or above. Filters have the booleans (AND, OR) operators, and they can be disabled and enabled.

How to query curated correlations ?

By default, it will show raw correlation data. Changing the index to “curated” will query only the curated correlations.

The screenshot shows the CCDB interface with a search filter set to 'curated'. The search results table displays 1,430 hits. The table columns include 'Source', 'target', and 'coeffCorTest'. The first row shows a correlation between 'rhamnes1212x1220' and 'perfluorooctanesulfonic acid' with a coefficient of 0.357.

For example, [PFOS query](#) returns a single curated correlation.

The screenshot shows the CCDB interface with a search filter set to 'PFOS'. The search results table displays 1 hit. The table columns include 'sourceNhanesChemicalName', 'targetNhanesChemicalName', and 'coeffCorTest'. The first row shows a correlation between '2-(N-ethyl-perfluorooctane sulfonamido) acetate' and 'perfluorooctane sulfonate' with a coefficient of 0.357.

Clicking on the zoom symbol will show the full document showing the correlation data and the interpretation data.

The screenshot shows the 'Document Details' for the PFOS query. The document details table shows the full correlation data and interpretation data. The table columns include 'f_id', 'f_index', 'f_score', 'f_type', 'f_biosystem', 'f_cids', 'f_coeffCorTest', 'f_coeffGLM', 'f_datasetdoi', 'f_datasetref', 'f_eclidtype', 'f_eclidid', 'f_enzyme', 'f_evidencedoi', 'f_evidenceref', 'f_gld', 'f_pairedCompleteCaseCount', and 'f_predecessor'.